

Reaction of Tetrachloromanganate(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands : Coordination Number Six and Eight

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A series of anionic complexes of manganese(II) of the type $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4\text{L}_2]$ and $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4\text{L}_2]$, where L is a nitrogen donor ligand were prepared. The compounds were characterised and possible stereochemistry deduced on the basis of analytical data, spectra (I.r. and electronic), conductivity and room temperature susceptibility measurements. They belong to dodecahedral and octahedral stereochemistry. Thermal decomposition studies of octacoordinated compounds at 100° reveal the loss of two ligand molecules leaving behind hexacoordinated products.

A great deal of interest has been evinced in the recent past for studying tetrachloromanganate(II) complexes¹⁻¹⁰ containing different cations such as alkali metal, ammonium, substituted ammonium, phosphonium, arsonium or pyridinium ions. From this laboratory, Das and Ramana Rao¹¹ have reported some mixed ligand anionic complexes of manganese(II) of the type $[\text{R}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4\text{Br}_2]$, $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_4\text{BrL}]$ and $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_4\text{BrL}_2]$, where L is pyridine or substituted pyridine and R is methyl or ethyl group. Nature of the cation can influence the coordination number of the metal in the anionic complex. Hence, in the present investigation tetrachloromanganate(II) anion having a bulky *n*-cetyl pyridinium as the cation was reacted with several nitrogen donor ligands and the results are reported in this communication.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade.

n-cetyl pyridinium tetrachloromanganate, $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4]$, was obtained by stirring a mixture of alcoholic solutions of manganese(II) chloride and *n*-cetyl pyridinium chloride in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The white microcrystalline compound was filtered under suction, washed with small amounts of absolute alcohol followed by ether and dried in

vacuo. The compound, $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4]$, was reacted with excess pyridine, substituted pyridine or isoquinoline by heating the reaction mixture slowly on a heating mantle stirring continuously till a clear solution is obtained. On cooling, the complex separated out in each case. It was then suction filtered, washed with absolute alcohol several times to ensure complete removal of excess ligand, followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*.

The composition of the complexes was established by estimating manganese and chloride by standard methods. Carbon and hydrogen were also estimated in case of octacoordinated compounds. The conductance measurements in nitrobenzene medium were carried out using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 with a dip type cell previously calibrated with KCl solution. The magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature with a Guoy balance and calculation was made computing diamagnetic corrections from Pascal's constants¹². The i.r. spectra of the compounds using nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls were recorded in the region $5000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics. The electronic spectra of solution in acetone or alcohol medium were obtained using a SP-500 spectrophotometer. The analytical data and electronic spectral data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF MANGANATE(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	M.P. (°C)	Mn(%) Found/Calc.	Cl(%) Found/Calc.	O(%) Found/Calc.	H(%) Found/Calc.	Λ_m (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M)
1. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4]$	60	6.56/6.81	17.70/17.60	—	—	66.6	5.80
2. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$	70	4.57/4.66	12.14/12.03	67.10/67.30	8.30/8.80	68.2	5.86
3. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\beta\text{-pic})_2]$	65	4.30/4.66	12.08/12.03	67.90/67.30	8.70/8.89	66.3	5.86
4. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{IQ})_2]$	63	4.16/4.15	10.80/10.73	70.20/70.87	8.50/7.93	65.9	5.56
5. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\alpha\text{-pic})_2]$	80	5.56/5.53	14.40/14.30	—	—	67.8	6.01
6. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{py})_2]$	73	5.79/5.70	14.72/14.71	—	—	66.0	5.93

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC(VISIBLE) SPECTRAL DATA OF MANGANATE(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Absorption bands (cm ⁻¹)
1. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4]$	27000, 23810, 22470, 20000.
2. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\alpha\text{-pic})_2]$	27000, 22730, 16670.
3. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{py})_2]$	27000, 22900, 17070.
4. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$	25640, 11220.
5. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\beta\text{-pic})_2]$	24390, 11220.
6. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{IQ})_2]$	25000, 11220.

Results and Discussion

The compounds reported in the present communication belong to two categories: six and eight coordinated. The coordination number and probable stereochemistry of these compounds has been suggested on the basis of their analytical data, infrared and electronic (visible) spectra, electrical conductivity in nitrobenzene and room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements. All the complexes are light yellow in colour.

As a direct consequence of 3d⁵ high spin configuration, there is no Jahn-Teller distortion for manganese(II). As a result, it is known to form either spin free tetrahedral, octahedral or dodecahedral complexes involving the use of 4s4p³, 4s4p³4d² or 4s4p³4d⁴ hybrid orbitals, respectively, for bonding. The complexes reported here are high-spin with magnetic moment values of 5.56–6.0 B.M. (Table 1) indicating the presence of five unpaired electrons, as expected for a 6A₁ ground state.

The infrared spectra of the complexes are quite illustrative. A sharp band obtained at 3050 cm⁻¹ in the hexachlorobutadiene mulls is assigned to the N–H stretching frequency of the *n*-cetyl pyridinium complexes as observed by Das and Ramana Rao¹³. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bands due to pyridine, substituted pyridine and isoquinoline obtained round about 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1560 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the coordination of these ligands through the nitrogen atom as suggested by Das and Ramana Rao¹¹.

The values of Δ_m obtained between 65.9–68.2 mhos (Table 1) in nitrobenzene medium indicate that the compounds are 2:1 electrolytes. The electronic spectral measurement is more useful for indicating the geometry of the compounds. Tetrahedral manganese(II) is expected to exhibit absorption bands in the visible region due to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$ at 20400 cm⁻¹; ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(G)$ at 22400 cm⁻¹; ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(G)$ at 23300 cm⁻¹, as reported by Forster and Goodgame¹⁴ and Cotton *et al.*⁸. In addition, it gives a band at 27500 at 26000 cm⁻¹ which, however, could not be unambiguously assigned, since three transitions to ${}^4T_2(D)$, ${}^4E(D)$ and ${}^4T_1(P)$ upper states, are expected in this region.

Liptay *et al.*¹⁵ obtained an absorption band at 16300 cm⁻¹ in addition to the bands at 22900 and 27000 cm⁻¹ for the octahedral compound $[\text{Mn}(\text{Py})_4(\text{CNS})_2]$. The bands obtained (Table 2) for the two six coordinated compounds, e.g., $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\alpha\text{-pic})_2]$ and $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{Py})_2]$, can be explained in terms of the octahedral nature of the compounds while the compound, $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4]$, aligns with the tetrahedral values reported. The three octacoordinated compounds, e.g., $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$, $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\beta\text{-pic})_2]$ and $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{IQ})_2]$, exhibit bands at 11220 cm⁻¹ and ~25000 cm⁻¹ which do not tally with the bands assigned to either tetrahedral or octahedral configurations. Hence they are attributable to a different configuration presumably dodecahedral for which no assignment was available earlier. Several octacoordinated complexes of first row transition metals have been reported^{16–18} earlier. Also, some neutral octacoordinated manganese(II) complexes were also known^{19,20}. Drummond and Wood¹⁸ have carried out the X-ray studies of tetraphenyl arsonium tetranitratomanganate(II), $[\text{Ph}_4\text{As}]_2[\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_4]$ and confirmed it to be monoclinic crystal with approximate D_{3d} (dodecahedral) symmetry. The three octacoordinated compounds in the present case are also presumably dodecahedral which has to be confirmed by X-ray studies.

Thermal Decomposition :

Thermal decomposition studies were carried out for the three octacoordinated compounds at 100°. The colour of the products was intense yellow. The different products obtained by thermal decomposition are as follows :

1. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$:

Obtained on heating $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$ at 100° to constant weight. Percentage loss of weight observed was 16.0 (theory, 15.8%). [Calculated for $\text{MnC}_{54}\text{H}_{90}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}_4$: Mn, 5.54%, Cl, 14.3%. Found : Mn 5.49%, Cl, 14.51%] Δ_m , 67.1 mhos in nitrobenzene medium.

2. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\beta\text{-pic})_2]$:

Obtained on heating $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\beta\text{-pic})_2]$ at 100° to constant weight. Percentage loss of weight observed was 15.9 (theory 15.8%). [Calculated for $\text{MnC}_{54}\text{H}_{90}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}_4$: Mn, 5.54%, Cl, 14.3% Found : Mn, 5.51%, Cl, 14.43%] Δ_m , 63.9 mhos in nitrobenzene medium.

3. $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{IQ})_2]$:

Obtained on heating $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4(\text{IQ})_2]$ at 100° to constant weight. Percentage loss of weight observed was 19.34 (theory, 19.54%). [Calculated for $\text{MnC}_{60}\text{H}_{90}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}_4$: Mn, 5.16%, Cl, 13.32%. Found : Mn, 5.13%, Cl, 13.01%] Δ_m , 61.2 mhos in nitrobenzene medium.

It is significant that in all the above cases, only two moles of the ligand are lost from $[n\text{-cepy}]_2[\text{MnCl}_4\text{L}_4]$ at 100° giving rise to a six-coordinated $[\text{MnCl}_4\text{L}_2]^-$ ion. This also indirectly suggests that in the original compound, the coordination number of manganese in the anionic complex is eight.

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